

The PROINS software for propeller hydrodynamics Reference manual

Francesco Salvatore and Danilo Calcagni

Marine Propulsion and Renewable Energy Lab

CNR-INM - Institute of Marine Engineering

Italian National Research Council

Via di Vallerano, 139 - 00128 Rome (Italy)

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Authors:	Francesco Salvatore and Danilo Calcagni
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Abstract:	<p>The input-output structure of the PRO-INS code is described in details. The code performs the hydrodynamic analysis of marine propellers and hydrokinetic turbines in arbitrary onset flow conditions under incompressible inviscid-flow assumptions. The code is based on a boundary element methodology (BEM) and in its more general version, it includes routines for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • trailing wake alignment • sheet cavitation pattern prediction • interactive boundary-layer viscous-flow analysis <p>The code is written in FORTRAN90 and is in-house developed by CNR-INM (formerly, CNR-INSEAN). The document also presents the software AUTOBLADE, to develop a 3D model of a hubbed screw propeller from tabulated input data, and build a surface mesh that is consistent with PROINS requirements.</p> <p>Details on the theoretical and computational methodology about the code are given in other reports and in the open literature.</p>

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1 Introduction

2 Overview of PRO-INS: Propeller Hydrodynamics code by INSEAN

This report provides an overview of PRO-INS, a propeller/turbine hydrodynamics computational model developed at CNR-INSEAN by staff from the Propulsion and Cavitation Laboratory (now Institute of Marine Engineering, INM).

The PRO-INS code is based on a Boundary Element Methodology (BEM) for inviscid flows around marine propellers or hydrokinetic turbines. Isolated rotors in a prescribed uniform flow as well as non-uniform inflow can be studied. In its more general version, PRO-INS includes routines for:

- trailing wake alignment
- sheet cavitation pattern prediction
- interactive boundary-layer viscous-flow analysis

The present manual provides a description of INput/Output (I/O) structures for the basic BEM algorithm and for additional modules for sheet cavitation pattern prediction and interactive boundary-layer viscous-flow analysis. Details of I/O structure for trailing wake alignment modelling is not addressed in this version of the manual.

Scope of the report is to describe PRO-INS code features that are relevant for running the code as stand-alone and through its coupling with a generic RANS code into a hybrid RANSE/BEM fashion. Code input and output structure, definitions and conventions on physical quantities, frames of reference used are described in details.

The document also presents the software AUTOBLADE, to develop a 3D model of a hubbed screw propeller from tabulated input data, and build a surface mesh that is consistent with PROINS requirements.

The PRO-INS and AUTOBLADE codes are written in Fortran 90 and executables are protected by a license key.

3 Hybrid RANS/BEM code interface and PRO-INS code

In the present report it is assumed that PRO-INS is the BEM code that can be run as a single code or can be coupled to an arbitrary RANS code into the hybrid RANS/BEM code. Thus, the specific structure of BEM to RANS interface implemented into the PRO-INS code is described here. For

applications in ship hydrodynamics, the hybrid RANS/BEM model is suitable to describe propeller-hull interaction. Dealing with marine turbine flows, the hybrid RANS/BEM model is relevant to simulate an array of turbines with each turbine operating in the perturbed wakefield induced by near turbines. Hereafter, term *rotor* is used to denote both a propeller or a turbine.

In the case of BEM code running as a single code, the flowfield around the rotor is studied by assuming the following:

- the rotor is immersed into an unbounded fluid region, and the velocity distribution incoming to the rotor is given as an input. This information can be determined from numerical as well as experimental data.

In the case of coupling with RANSE, the interface with the BEM code is developed following basic assumptions.

- RANS and BEM codes are independent and communicate only via input/output quantities stored into formatted files.
- A velocity distribution evaluated by the RANS code over a plane perpendicular to propeller/turbine axis and located upstream the rotor disc plane is used to evaluate the inflow to the rotor. This inflow is an input quantity for BEM code calculations.
- A body-force distribution is evaluated by the BEM code over the same plane introduced above. This body-force distribution is an input quantity for RANS code calculations.

The inflow to the rotor and the rotor-induced body-force distribution represent core quantities to be exchanged between the RANS and BEM solvers.

Both rotor inflow and body force distributions are evaluated over the same plane normal to the rotor axis and located at a prescribed axial position in front of the rotor.

Hereafter, this plane is referred to as the *inflow plane*.

4 Definitions and conventions on physical quantities

In order to have a consistent data communication between hull-flow solver and propeller-flow solver it is necessary to have an exact correspondance of physical quantities exchanged by the two codes. Propeller flow quantities relevant for the interface between codes are:

- advance coefficient: $J = V/nD$;
- pressure coefficient: $C_p = (p - p_\infty)/\frac{1}{2}\rho n^2 D^2$;
- propeller thrust coefficient: $K_T = T/\rho n^2 D^4$;

- propeller torque coefficient: $K_Q = Q/\rho n^2 D^5$.
- cavitation number: $\sigma_n = (p_\infty - p_v)/\frac{1}{2}\rho n^2 D^2$;
- Reynolds number: $Rn = nD^2/\nu$;
- Froude number: $Fn = nD/\sqrt{gD}$;

where D, n denote respectively propeller diameter (in meter) and rotational speed (in rps), V is the reference speed of the undisturbed flow, T, Q are respectively propeller thrust (in Newton) and torque (in Newton meter), whereas ρ, ν are, respectively, water density and kinematic viscosity; finally, p_∞ is a reference freestream pressure, and p_v is the vapor pressure.

Quantities above are typical for marine propellers. For marine turbines it is common to use also the following non-dimensional parameters, where $\omega = 2\pi n$ is the rotor angular velocity, R is the rotor diameter and $A = \pi R^2$:

- turbine tip speed ratio (TSR); $\lambda = \omega R/V$;
- turbine thrust coefficient: $C_T = T/0.5\rho AV^2$;
- turbine torque coefficient: $C_Q = Q/0.5\rho AV^2 R$;
- turbine power coefficient: $C_P = Q\omega/0.5\rho AV^3$;

The following relationships among propeller coefficients and turbine coefficients hold:

$$\begin{aligned} TSR &= \frac{\pi}{J}; & C_T &= \frac{8}{\pi^3} TSR^2 K_T; \\ C_Q &= \frac{16}{\pi^3} TSR^2 K_Q; & C_P &= \frac{16}{\pi^3} TSR^3 K_Q; \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Another fundamental input quantity, the inflow to the propeller/turbine, is discussed in detail in Section 7 below.

All above quantities are non-dimensional to reflect that equations solved by the PRO-INS code are written in non-dimensional form. Non-dimensional values are determined from dimensional ones according to typical conventions used for propeller/turbine flow analysis.

In ship hydrodynamics, When interfacing propeller flow codes and hull flow codes, special attention should be paid to different conventions used. Reference quantities used to derive non-dimensional data in the PRO-INS propeller-flow code and in some ship-flow codes are compared in Table 1 (taken from Deliverable D4.3.9).

It should be noted that the inflow to the rotor and the rotor-induced velocity (see Section ??) are made non-dimensional with respect to the free stream flow speed, V . This way, exchanged velocity

quantity	ship-flow	PRO-INS propeller-flow
length	hull length, L_{PP}	propeller diameter, D
inflow velocity	ship speed, V	ship speed, V
time	-	propeller rev. period, $1/n$

Table 1: Comparison of typical reference quantities to derive non-dimensional data in ship-flow codes and in the PRO-INS propeller-flow code.

fields are made non-dimensional in the same way typically used in RANS codes.

All other physical quantities representing flow velocity within the PRO-INS code are reduced to non-dimensional through the reference velocity nD that typically describes blade tip flow.

5 Frames of reference

Two Cartesian frames of reference are used in the PRO-INS code to describe geometrical as well as flow quantities.

Rotor geometry and potential-flow governing equations are expressed with respect to a frame of reference rigidly connected to the rotating rotor. This frame of reference is referred to as *Rotating Frame of Reference* (RFR), and corresponding coordinates are x, y, z . The x -axis is aligned with the rotor axis and is pointing downstream. The z -axis is aligned with the blade reference line, and the y -axis is orthogonal to both x and z . The rotor rotates about the x -axis. Although the origin of RFR is left arbitrary, it may be convenient to have $x = 0$ corresponding to the intersection of blade reference line and rotor axis.

In addition, a fixed (*i.e.*, non rotating) frame of reference is used to define the inflow to the rotor, the rotor induced velocity and the body-force distribution associated to rotor blade loading. This frame of reference is referred to as *Fixed Frame of Reference* (FFR) and corresponding coordinates are x_F, y_F, z_F .

Origins of both RFR and FFR, as well as x and x_F axes coincide. During a rotor revolution at rotational speed $\omega = 2\pi n$, axis z forms an angle $\psi = \omega t$ with axis z_F . This angle is positive for right-handed rotor and negative for left-handed rotor.

Both rotating and fixed frames of reference are sketched in Fig. 1.

For further reference, a cylindrical grid (O, x_F, r, θ) can be associated to the Cartesian grids defined above. Specifically, cylindrical components r and θ and Cartesian components y_F, z_F are related by the following expressions (see Fig. 2)

$$\begin{aligned} r &= \sqrt{y_F^2 + z_F^2}; \\ \theta &= \arctg(y_F/z_F). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Definition of rotating and fixed frames of reference: Left: righthanded rotor observed from suction side. Right: side view.

6 Computational grid

The PRO-INS code can perform rotor flow simulations once a computational grid describing the propeller surface has been provided as input. In fact, PRO-INS does not include a grid generation tool. The BLADEGEN code has been developed by INSEAN to build computational grids in the format requested by PRO-INS: see BLADEGEN manual for details.

Recalling the PRO-INS code is based on a Boundary Integral Methodology, no computational grid discretizing the fluid region around the rotor is required.

The PRO-INS code requires in input a structured grid by which the surface of the rotor is discretized into quadrilateral elements. Triangular elements should be avoided because of possible problems when evaluating influence coefficients. Both planar and non planar elements are allowed.

Assuming that all blades are identical, only the geometry of one blade is necessary (*key blade*). All other blades are duplicated automatically by the code. In case of hubbed rotor, the same approach is used for the hub surface. Only one hub sector, *i.e.*, a surface covering in peripheral direction an angle equal to $360/Z$ degrees (with Z the number of blades), is required (*key hub sector*). All other hub sectors are duplicated automatically by the code. An example of a four-bladed rotor and the corresponding surface grid generated as input to the PRO-INS code is shown in Fig. 3. Coordinates of grid nodes are referred to the RFR defined above.

First, grid nodes on one blade are given. Nodes are distributed on blade sections at constant radius. Blade surface is considered as a single patch combining both suction and pressure sides. On each

Figure 2: Cartesian grid (O, x_F, y_F, z_F) and cylindrical grid (O, x_F, r, θ) defined on plane at constant x_F , *i.e.*, normal to propeller axis (observed from downstream).

radial section, nodes are ordered from blade trailing edge to leading edge through blade suction side and from leading edge to trailing edge on pressure side. Trailing edge nodes on pressure and suction sides are repeated, whereas the leading edge node is not repeated.

Radial sections are ordered from blade root section to blade tip section. In case of hubbed rotor, blade root section has non-zero thickness and blade nodes define the intersection of blade surface with hub surface. In case of hubless rotor, blade root section is forced by the code to have zero thickness, *i.e.*, sectional nodes on suction and pressure sides in the same relative position with respect to section leading edge coincide. Similarly, blade tip section has zero thickness.

It is important to observe that zero-chord blade tip sections should be avoided because of possible problems with triangular discretization elements. If required, a fictitious non-zero chord tip sections should be defined. A practical approach is to cut the actual blade geometry at $(100 - \epsilon)\%$ of blade radius, with ϵ arbitrary quantity in the range of 0.05-0.5.

Next, grid nodes on one hub surface sector are given. Hub grid is made by longitudinal nodal lines and peripheral nodal lines: see Fig. 3. In peripheral direction grid nodes are ordered in counterclockwise direction as seen from downstream. In longitudinal direction grid nodes are ordered from upstream to downstream.

In case of hubless rotor, hub-nodes dataset is not read by the PRO-INS code. Selection of hubbed or

Figure 3: Computational grid in input to the PRO-INS code and definition of grid-nodes indices. Left: key-blade. Right: full grid with key-blade and key-hub sectors in evidence.

hubless rotor flow analysis is made by code user through a dedicated input variable in file `icav.dat`, see section 10. The input file providing the rotor surface computational grid must have a structure described in Section 8.1 below.

In addition to rotor (blades and hub) surface, BEM calculations also require a definition of the rotor-induced trailing wake surface. Recalling potential flow theory, this surface is generated by path of flow particles shed by all propeller blades trailing edges. This surface is generally referred to simply as rotor (potential) wake. The wake geometry is built by the PRO-INS code, and hence it is not required as input grid. Different helicoidal wake shapes can be determined using dedicated input variables in file `icav.dat`, see Section 10. Wake surface discretization parameters are the number of elements in radial direction (this must be equal to same parameter for blade surface discretization) and number of elements in streamwise (longitudinal) direction over a wake portion describing a 360 degrees revolution (one wake spiral).

As an example, the computational grid built to discretize the surface of a helicoidal trailing wake generated downstream a four-bladed marine propeller is shown in Fig. 4.

The helicoidal surface used in calculations can be tailored to the specific problem addressed. The surface is assumed to be composed of two distinct parts: the *near wake*, extending from blade trailing edge to some position downstream, and the *far wake*, extending beyond this position to the downstream end of the surface. Theoretically, the wake should be extended to an infinite distance downstream the rotor. In contrast to this, the discretized portion of this surface has a

Figure 4: Computational grid for a four-bladed propeller with helicoidal-shaped trailing wake. For clarity, only the wake shed by one blade is plotted.

limited extension. Once the pitch of the helicoidal surface is given, the longitudinal extension of the discretised wake is defined by the number of revolutions about the axis. For instance, in Fig. 4 a wake portion corresponding to one revolution is shown. In the PRO-INS code, the length of the discretised portion of the wake is defined by the user by indicating a number of revolutions.

The boundary between near and far wake is determined as the number of revolutions in the near wake surface. The location of the boundary between near and far wake is imposed and cannot be modified by the user. Near and far wake surfaces present a different definition of the wake pitch. Specifically,

- in the far wake, the wake pitch ϕ_{FW} is evaluated as a user-defined linear combination of nose-tail line pitch at each blade section $\phi_{NT}(r)$ and of the *hydrodynamic pitch* ϕ_j of the onset flow, that is the pitch of streamlines described by flow particles with axial speed equal to freestream velocity V and rotational speed equal to rotor rotational speed $\omega = 2\pi n$. Note that ϕ_j/D equals the advance coefficient J ;
- in the near wake, the wake pitch is a linear combination between the a pitch representative of blade sections and the far wake pitch ϕ_{FW} . The pitch representative of blade sections can be chosen in two ways: (i) pitch of midline between tangents to blade suction and pressure sides at trailing edge (ϕ_{TE}) or (ii) pitch of the nose-tail line, ϕ_{NT} .

See Section 10 for details on PRO-INS code input variables defining parameters to build the discretised wake surface.

7 Hull wake and inflow to the propeller/turbine

A fundamental quantity in input to the PRO-INS code is the inflow to the rotor, that is the velocity distribution incoming to the rotor plane. Such an inflow can be spatially uniform in case of open water conditions or non homogeneous in case of rotor operating behind a ship hull. The inflow to the rotor plane is used in the PRO-INS code to evaluate boundary conditions on the rotor surface (see details on boundary conditions in BEM models).

Dealing with flow calculations by the hybrid RANS/BEM code, it is assumed that the velocity field in the rotor region, and in particular the incoming flow to the rotor plane, is predicted by the RANS code and then passed as input to the BEM code.

When the BEM code is run as single code, the velocity field is assumed to be prescribed by existing data that can be either numerical or experimental.

The inflow to the rotor is defined with respect to the fixed frame of reference FFR defined in Section 5. Denoting by \mathbf{v}_T the *total* velocity distribution incoming to the rotor disc, *i.e.*, free-stream velocity plus hull perturbation including rotor effects (if present), and by V the intensity of freestream velocity (*i.e.*, vessel speed), the inflow velocity defect \mathbf{w} is defined as

$$\mathbf{w} = V\mathbf{e}_x - \mathbf{v}_T. \quad (3)$$

The distribution of the velocity defect \mathbf{w} over the rotor plane is requested as input by PRO-INS code. Specifically, components referred to the cylindrical coordinate system (O, x_F, r, θ) are to be given:

$$\begin{aligned} w_x &= \mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x = V - \mathbf{v}_T \cdot \mathbf{e}_x \\ w_\theta &= \mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{e}_\theta = \mathbf{v}_T \cdot \mathbf{e}_\theta \\ w_r &= \mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{e}_r = \mathbf{v}_T \cdot \mathbf{e}_r \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_\theta, \mathbf{e}_r$ denote respectively, unit vectors along axial direction x_F , tangential direction θ and radial direction r (see Figs. 2 and 5). Signs of inflow components w_x, w_θ, w_r are defined with respect to unit vectors $\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_\theta, \mathbf{e}_r$.

In Eqs (3) and (5) it is assumed that free-stream velocity and rotor axis are aligned. In the present version of the PRO-INS code, the general case of rotor axis arbitrarily inclined by angle α_{shaft} with respect to the free-stream velocity of a ship in straight ahead motion is not allowed and the condition $\alpha_{shaft} = 0$ is enforced.

The generalization to take into account for non-zero shaft angles will be provided in future versions of the code.

In case of PRO-INS running in stand-alone mode, that is without coupling to RANS, the assignment of either uniform or non-uniform inflow to the rotor is also required.

In particular, open water conditions correspond to uniform onset flow at constant speed, $\mathbf{v}_T = V\mathbf{e}_x$.

Figure 5: Example of plane where the inflow to rotor is defined and conventions about grid nodes indices i and j .

In this case, recalling Eq. (3), all components of the velocity defect distribution w are zero.

$$\begin{aligned}w_x &= 0 \\w_\theta &= 0 \quad (\text{uniform onset flow}) \\w_r &= 0\end{aligned}$$

See Section 8.2 for a complete description of the structure of the input file dedicated to the inflow to the rotor.

8 PRO-INS code input data

Input data required by the PRO-INS code can be divided into the following classes:

- BEM model control parameters and rotor operating conditions;
- hybrid-code run control parameters;
- rotor computational grid;
- rotor inflow;
- self-propulsion test data (only for ship flow simulations).

PRO-INS code input data are described here below, whereas next section is dedicated to output data. Unless specified, all data are non-dimensional as described in Section 4.

The complete list of I/O files is summarized in Section 11.

8.1 Computational grid

The rotor surface computational grid used by the PRO-INS code has been described in Section 6. Coordinates of computational grid nodes are referred to the Rotating Frame of Reference RFR, in which the rotor is fixed.

Name and location of this file are specified by code user through dedicated input variable in file 'icav.dat,' see section 10.

The input file of PRO-INS code providing the computational grid is formatted and must have a structure compatible with data read statements in Fortran given here below.

```
read(geounit,*) dumint
read(geounit,*) mbladenod, nbladenod, dumint
read(geounit,*) mhubnod, nhubnod, dumint
read(geounit,*)
&          ((xblade(i,j), i=0,mblade), j=0,nblade),
&          ((yblade(i,j), i=0,mblade), j=0,nblade),
&          ((zblade(i,j), i=0,mblade), j=0,nblade)
read(geounit,*)
&          ((xhub(i,j), i=0,mhub), j=0,nhub),
&          ((yhub(i,j), i=0,mhub), j=0,nhub),
&          ((zhub(i,j), i=0,mhub), j=0,nhub)
```

Read statements refer to file unit `geounit` dynamically associated to the input file where the computational grid is stored. The other Fortran variables correspond to:

```
mbladenod = number of nodes on key-blade in chordwise direction
nbladenod = number of nodes on key-blade in spanwise direction
mhubnod   = number of nodes on hub-sector in peripheral direction
nhubnod   = number of nodes on hub-sector in longitudinal direction
mblade    = mbladenod - 1
nblade    = nbladenod - 1
mhub      = mhubnod - 1
nhub      = nhubnod - 1
dumint    = dummy integer value (not used by code)
xblade, yblade, zblade = arrays of components of grid nodes on blade
xhub, yhub, zhub      = arrays of components of grid nodes on hub
```

8.2 Inflow to the rotor

Recalling Section 3, the inflow to the rotor is an input quantity to the PRO-INS code. In particular, in case of hybrid RANS/BEM calculations, it is expected that the inflow results from hull flow predictions by RANS.

Refer to Section 7 for the exact definition of the inflow to the rotor considered here. In the same file, both coordinates of points where velocity is evaluated and values of velocity components are given. All these quantities are referred to the cylindrical grid (O, r, θ) introduced in Eq. (2), Section 5, and depicted in Fig. 5.

Name and location of file storing the inflow to the rotor are specified by code user through dedicated input variable in file 'icav.dat,' see section 10.

This file is formatted and must have a structure compatible with data read statements in Fortran given here below.

```
read(infunit,*) nri, nthetai, nmgr, pseudoloop, istephyb, hulldrag
read(infunit,*) (ri(i),i=1,nri)
do j = 1, nthetai
  read(infunit,*) thetai(j), (ua(i,j),i=1,nri)
enddo
read(infunit,*)
read(infunit,*) (ri(i),i=1,nri)
do j = 1, nthetai
  read(infunit,*) thetai(j), (ut(i,j),i=1,nri)
enddo
read(infunit,*)
read(infunit,*) (ri(i),i=1,nri)
do j = 1, nthetai
  read(infunit,*) thetai(j), (ur(i,j),i=1,nri)
enddo
```

Read statements refer to file unit `infunit` dynamically associated to the input file where inflow data are stored. Fortran variables in the read statement block above are:

nri = number of inflow-grid points in radial direction
nthetai = number of inflow-grid points in peripheral direction
ri = array of radial locations of inflow-grid points
thetai = array of peripheral locations of inflow-grid points [deg]
ua = array of inflow velocity component along x
ut = array of inflow velocity component along theta
ur = array of inflow velocity component along r

Data above are common to using BEM in stand-alone mode as well as in coupling with RANSE. Next, other parameters from the first line are specific for the hybrid RANSE/BEM coupling:

nmgr = index of grid level for full multi-grid RANSE
pseudoloop = index of pseudo-time loop in RANSE solver
istephyb = index of hybrid RANSE/BEM coupling step
hulldrag = ship hull resistance coefficient calculated by RANSE

It is important to note that definition of inflow to the rotor and corresponding data read as indicated above is necessary also in case of analysis of rotor in uniform inflow, see Section 7.

9 PRO-INS code output data

Data generated by the PRO-INS code can be divided into the following classes:

- rotor-flow physical quantities predicted by BEM;
- rotor-hull interaction fields: body-force distribution and rotor-induced velocity;
- self-propulsion test exchange data;
- hybrid-code run control parameters;
- BEM model execution temporary data.

PRO-INS code output data are described here below. Unless specified, all data are non-dimensional as described in Section 4.

The complete list of I/O files is summarized in Section 11.

10 BEM model input data in the PRO-INS code

File `icav.dat` collects all the information required to perform a rotor-flow calculation using the PRO-INS code. Most of these data are independent from the interface to the RANS code and are required also if the PRO-INS code is run in stand-alone mode. Other data specifically address the interface to the RANS code in the hybrid code. Unless specified, all numerical data values are non-dimensional with respect to reference quantities as indicated in Section 4.

An example of file `icav.dat` is given here. On each line, value assigned to input quantity, name of corresponding Fortran variable, and a brief description is given.

```
'../GRIDS/E779A_12x12a01.geo' ! GEOFIL = Geometry file name .....
'rotor' ! BODYTYPE = Geometry type (Propeller/turbine) .....
  4 ! BLADES = Number of blades .....
  1 ! HUBFLAG = Hub-including analysis [0/1] .....
0.160000E+07 ! RED = Diameter-based Reynolds no. ....
0.227270E+00 ! PROPDIAM = Ref. Propeller diameter [m].....
  0 ! START = Restart option [0/1].....
'./proins-a01' ! STARTIFILE = Name of restart file .....
  0 ! KCOEFSAV = Available influence coefficients [0/1]....
'.' ! DIRNAME = Directory of infl. coefficient files.....
0.300000E+01 ! HTURN = No. of wake revolutions .....
  60 ! NELWPT = No. of wake panels per turn .....
  1 ! KPREWAK = Type of wake geometry .....
0.100000E+00 ! WAKEPITCH = Wake pitch [<0: calc; blade=0<>1=inflow]..
  -1 ! ITMAX = No. of time steps .....
'./uni_wake.hinf' ! INFFILE = Viscous Inflow file name .....
0.880000E+00 ! VIN = Advance coefficient.....
  0 ! HYBKIND = Type RANS/BEM coupl [0=BEM,1=SS,2=SU,3=UU]
'./pot_dummy.inf' ! PINFILE = Potential Inflow file name .....
-.320000E+00 ! XINFLOWDISC= Axial position inflow disc .....
  5 ! NRIBEM = No. of radial nodes on potential disc ....
  13 ! NTHETAIBEM = No. of azimuth nodes on potential disc ...
  0 ! SPTKIND = Self-prop test including analysis [0/1] ..
'./E779A_ow.dat' ! POWFILE = Prop O.W./Turbine polar file name
0.000000E+00 ! ALPHASHAFT = Shaft angle wrt. horizontal [deg] .....
'--- CAV DATA ---'
  1 ! CAVRUN = Cavitation analysis [0/1].....
  1 ! ITCAV = First time step of cavitation anal. ....
0.300000E+02 ! DELTHCAV = Angular ext. of cavitating-wake [deg].....
  0 ! NTIPCAV = No. of tip panels with no cav-analysis....
  1 ! MCLECINI = Cavity leading edge (init. guess) .....
  9 ! MCCINI = Cavity trailing edge (init. guess) .....
0.151500E+01 ! SIGMAC = Cavitation number .....
0.999000E+06 ! FND = Froude number .....
0.999000E+01 ! ZREF = Depth of rotor axis .....
  15 ! NSTEPEXT = No. step external loop .....
  8 ! NSTEPINT = No. step internal loop .....
0.100000E-03 ! LIMRESSHAPE= Max. error of external residual .....
0.500000E-03 ! LIMRESFLOW = Max. error of internal residual .....
  1 ! KCLOFUN = Kind of cavity closure .....
0.300000E+00 ! ALAMBDA = Extension of cavity-wake .....
```


0.500000E+00 ! ACOEF = Coeff. of closure correction
0.200000E+01 ! AGAMMA = Expon. of closure correction

```
'--- IBL DATA -----'  
  0          ! IBLRUN      = Boundary-layer analysis [0/1] .....  
999          ! ITIBL       = First time step of viscous analysis .....  
  1          ! MWAKEIBL    = No. of viscous-wake panels .....  
  3          ! NTIPIBL    = No. of tip panels with no ibl-analysis....  
0.500000E+00 ! ALPHATV      = Relaxation factor for transp. veloc. ....  
  1          ! KIBL        = Kind of boundary-layer model .....  
'--- RUN DATA -----'  
'./          ' ! DIRLICENSE = Directory of license file
```

It may be noted that data are grouped into four main blocks:

- run specification parameters and basic BEM model parameters
- cavitation model parameters (CAV)
- interactive boundary-layer model parameters (IBL)
- code license parameters

In the following tables, all variables are briefly described. FORTRAN type and admissible (or simply meaningful) range are also given.

<i>name</i>	<i>Fortran type</i>	<i>range</i>	<i>description</i>
GEOFILE	Character	-	Name and path to rotor grid file
BODYTYPE	Character	'propeller' or 'turbine'	Type of rotor
BLADES	Integer	1 to 10	Number of blades
HUBFLAG	Integer	0, 1	Flag to select hub inclusion: 0 = hubless rotor analysis; 1 = hubbed rotor analysis
RED	Real	> 0	Reynolds number, $Rn_D = nD^2/\nu$
PROPDIAM	Real	> 0	Propeller diameter [m]
START	Integer	0, 1	Flag to select restart option: 0 = start run from scratch; 1 = start run from restart file
STARTIFILE	Character	-	Name and path of restart file
KCOEFSAV	Integer	0, 1	Flag to select influence coeffs. option: 0 = compute influence coeffs.; 1 = use existing influence coeffs.
DIRNAME	Character	-	Path to influence coeffs. directory

Table 2: PRO-INS code: input variables related with the BEM model and the interface to RANS.

<i>name</i>	<i>Fortran type</i>	<i>range</i>	<i>description</i>
HTURNS	Real	> 0	Number of wake revolutions
NELWPT	Integer	≥ 1	Number of wake elements per turn in streamwise direction
KPREWAK	Integer	1, 2, -2	Type of prescribed wake model: 1 = helicoidal, unstretched 2 = helicoidal, body-fitted stretched -2 = read from input file 'freewake.geo'
WAKEPITCH	Real	0 to 1	Pitch of helicoidal prescribed far wake
ITMAX	Integer	≥ -1	Number of time steps: -1 = steady-state analysis 0 = do not perform time-loop > 1 = time-loop with ITMAX steps
INFFILE	Character	-	Name and path to (viscous) inflow file
VIN	Real	≥ 0	Advance coefficient, $J = V/nD$
HYBKIND	Integer	0,1,2,3,4	Type of hybrid RANS/BEM coupling: 0 = BEM only 1 = steady RANS and steady BEM 2,3 = steady RANS and unsteady BEM 4 = unsteady RANS and unsteady BEM
PINFILE	Character	-	Name and path to potential inflow file
XINFLOWDISC	Real	$-\infty$ to ∞	Axial location of inflow plane
NRIBEM	Integer	≥ 0	Number of points in radial direction on reduced inflow plane grid
NTHETAIBEM	Integer	≥ 0	Number of points in peripheral direction on reduced inflow plane grid
SPTKIND	Integer	0, 1	Flag to select self-propulsion test (SPT): 0 = skip self-propulsion test 1 = perform self-propulsion test
POWFILE	Character	-	Name and path of prop. open water file or of turbine section lift, drag file
ALPHASHAFT	Real	-90° to 90°	Shaft angle wrt. free-stream vel. [deg]

Table 3: PRO-INS code: input variables related with the BEM model and the interface to RANS. *Cont'd*).

<i>name</i>	<i>Fortran type</i>	<i>range</i>	<i>description</i>
CAVRUN	Integer	0, 1	Flag to select cavitation analysis: 0 = non-cavitating flow analysis 1 = cavitating flow analysis
ITCAV	Integer	> 0	Time step when cavitation model is switched on
DELTHCAV	Real	≥ 0	Angular portion of wake turn where super-cavitation modelling is checked [deg]
NTIPCAV	Integer	≥ 0	Number of radial strips at blade tip where cavitation modelling is skipped
MCLECINI	Integer	-1 or > 0	Location of initial guess cavity detachment: -1 = not prescribed; > 0 prescribed at MCLECINI node after LE
MCCINI	Integer	≥ 1	Location of initial guess cavity trailing edge
SIGMAC	Real	> 0	Cavitation index, $\sigma_n = (p - p_v)/1/2\rho n^2 D^2$
FND	Real	> 0	Froude number, $Fn_D = V/\sqrt{gD}$
ZREF	Real	> 0	Distance of rotor axis from free-surface
NSTEP EXT	Integer	≥ 1	Maximum number of iterations, external loop
NSTEP INT	Integer	≥ 1	Maximum number of iterations, internal loop
LIMRESSHAPE	Real	> 0	Maximum allowed error on cavity area to match convergence
LIMRESFLOW	Real	> 0	Maximum allowed error on cavity boundary conds. to match convergence
KCLOFUN	Integer	1, 2	Type of cavity closure model
ALAMBDA	Real	0 to 1	Coefficient λ in cavity closure model
ACOE F	Real	0 to 1	Coefficient A in cavity closure model
AGAMMA	Real	> 0	Coefficient γ in cavity closure model

Table 4: PRO-INS code: input variables related with the cavitation model.

<i>name</i>	<i>Fortran type</i>	<i>range</i>	<i>description</i>
IBLRUN	Integer	0, 1	Flag to select boundary-layer analysis: 0 = inviscid-flow analysis 1 = IBL: interactive boundary layer
ITIBL	Integer	> 0	Time step when IBL model is switched on
MWAKEIBL	Integer	0 to MWAKE	No. of viscous-wake panels
NTIPIBL	Integer	≥ 0	Number of radial strips at blade tip where boundary-layer modelling is skipped
ALPHATV	Real	0 to 1	Relaxation factor for transpiration velocity
KIBL	Integer	0, 1	Kind of boundary-layer model
DIRLICENSE	Character		name and path to PRO-INS license file

Table 5: PRO-INS code: input variables related with the interactive boundary layer model and the license file.

10.1 Preparing file `icav.dat` to evaluate isolated rotor performance by BEM

Definition of rotor geometry

Name and path of the rotor grid file is specified through variable `GEOFILE`. In this file only key-blade and key-hub sector nodes are given. The number of rotor blades is specified by `BLADES`. Propeller diameter (in meters) is given by `PROPDIAM`.

Setting `HUBFLAG = 1`, a hubbed rotor is modelled. If `HUBFLAG = 0`, a hubless rotor with blades having zero thickness at root section is modelled. In this case, reading key-hub nodes from file `GEOFILE` is skipped.

`ALPHASHAFT` denotes the inclination of the shaft axis with respect to the horizontal line (in deg). Non-zero shaft angles are not allowed in the present version of the code.

Definition of trailing wake model

Trailing wakes generated by each rotor blade are built according to analytical models as specified by `KPREWAK`. If `KPREWAK = 1`, an helicoidal wake is generated with uniform distribution of discretization elements in streamwise direction. If `KPREWAK = 2`, an helicoidal wake with panels stretched towards the blade trailing edge is generated. If `KPREWAK = -2`, the wake geometry is read from an input file named 'freewake.geo'. If this file is not found in the current directory, the run stops. For steady flow, both `KPREWAK = 1, +2, -2` is allowed. For unsteady flow, `KPREWAK = 2` is not consistent, because wake elements cannot be stretched in the streamwise direction.

The pitch of the far wake portion can be adjusted by variable `WAKEPITCH`.

If `WAKEPITCH = 0`, wake pitch equals pitch of nose-tail line of rotor blade sections, whereas `WAKEPITCH = 1` yields wake pitch equal the hydrodynamic pitch of the incoming flow. Values between 0 and 1 can be used to evaluate wake pitch as a weighted average between values above.

The pitch of the near wake portion linearly varies between blade pitch at trailing edge (`KPREWAK = 1`) or blade pitch of nose-tail line (`KPREWAK = 2`) and pitch in the far wake portion of the wake. The extension of the trailing wake is given specifying a number of helix revolutions (or turns), variable `HTURNS`. The number of discretization elements in streamwise direction per helix revolution is `NELWPT`.

Typical values: $3 < HTURNS < 4$, and $40 < NELWPT < 120$ (actual value should be related to chordwise discretization on blade: the finer blade discretization, the finer wake discretization).

Wetted flow conditions

Advance coefficient is given by variable `VIN`, and Reynolds number based on rotational speed is given by `RED`. The inflow to the rotor is read from file `INFFILE`.

Steady and unsteady flow analysis

Variable `ITMAX` denotes the maximum number of time steps to be evaluated. The number of time steps per revolution is implicitly given by `NELWPT`, equal to number of discretization elements in streamwise direction per helix revolution (see above).

If `ITMAX = -1`, a steady-state calculation is assumed.

Note that choosing steady or unsteady flow simulations should be associated with adequate definition

of inflow to the rotor. In particular, note that the inflow has to be specified also in case of uniform onset flow.

If $ITMAX = -1$ and a non-uniform inflow is given through file INFFILE, then the inflow is averaged in circumferential direction to force steady flow conditions.

Influence coefficients management

In general, $KCOEFSAV = 0$ and influence coefficients are evaluated once a new run is started. If influence coefficients are available from previous runs using *exactly* the same geometry of body and wake, $KCOEFSAV = 1$ allows to use existing coefficients stored in a directory whose name and path are specified by variable DIRNAME. It must be noted that if WAKEPITCH is not zero, the geometry of the wake depends on the advance coefficient VIN.

Restart options

In case of unsteady flow calculations, solution quantities evaluated at a given time step are saved into restart files named 'BASENAME-IT.newrst', where variable BASENAME is a string specified by user to identify the ongoing run, whereas IT is a number denoting time step. Setting $START = 0$, flow calculations by PRO-INS start from scratch. If $START = 1$, and a restart file with name and path given by STARTIFILE exists, the calculation starts from time step $IT+1$ and continues until the maximum number of time steps ITMAX is reached. Note that restart option and influence coefficients options can be combined to reduce computational efforts.

Hybrid RANS/BEM model options

Variable HYBKIND is used to specify the type of coupling between BEM and RANS solvers. Open water rotor flow analysis by BEM is achieved setting $HYBKIND = 0$. In this case, variables XINFLOWDISC, NRIBEM, NTHETAIBEM, SPTKIND, can be set to dummy values. In addition, files PINFILE, POWFILE are not used, and dummy values can be also given. If HYBKIND is not zero, interaction with RANS is expected. See dedicated descriptions.

Cavitating flow modelling

If $CAVRUN = 0$, only wetted flow analysis is performed. If $CAVRUN = 1$, the cavitation model is switched on. If $CAVRUN = 1$ and a steady-state analysis is performed, a first step with wetted flow conditions is performed. Then a second step with cavitating flow condition is calculated. These two steps are labelled like time steps no. 1 (wetted flow) and 2 (cavitating flow). In case $CAVRUN = 1$ and steady flow, variable ITCAV is not used and can be set to a dummy value. If $CAVRUN = 1$ and an unsteady flow analysis is performed, the cavitation model is switched on at time step given by ITCAV.

Cavitation model: flow conditions

Cavitation number σ_n value is given by SIGMAC. Froude number is given by FND. ZREF denotes the vertical distance of rotor axis from free surface. If free surface effects are neglected, FND can be set to a very large value and ZREF to a dummy value.

Cavitation model: parameters

Cavitating flow analysis with bubble extending downstream the blade trailing edge is allowed. Variable DELTHCAV defines the portion of trailing wake downstream the blade trailing edge where cavitating flow appearance is tested. $DELTHCAV > 0$ can be also used to allow prediction of cavitation in the tip-vortex region. This value is expressed in degrees. Typical value can be set between 10 and 45 degrees, to allow for cavities extended in the tip-vortex region, and higher values in case of flows at very low cavitation number SIGMAC.

Variable NTIPCAV denotes the number of chordwise stripes from blade tip to inner sections where cavitation model is disabled. $NTIPCAV = 0$ means that cavitation modelling is allowed on all blade sections. In some particular cases, NTIPCAV greater than zero can help to increase run robustness because failure of cavitation model at blade tip is prevented.

Variable MCLECINI denotes the location of guessed cavity inception point at blade leading edge. This location is expressed as the index of chordwise element from leading edge to trailing edge. $MCLECINI = 1$, denoting cavity inception at blade leading edge is the suggested value.

Variable MCCINI denotes the location of guessed cavity trailing edge. This location is expressed as the index of chordwise element from leading edge to trailing edge. Suggested value is MCCINI equal to one half of blade discretization elements in chordwise direction from leading to trailing edge.

Two iterative loops are associated to the numerical solution of the cavitation model. Convergence of the iterative procedures is established when suitable error quantities fall below given values LIMRESSHAPE and LIMRESFLOW. Typical values for these two variables are equal or lower than $1 \times E^{-3}$.

Variables NSTEPEXT and NSTEPINT denote maximum number of steps related to iterative loops to solve the cavitation model. Typical values are $5 < NSTEPEXT < 15$ and $NSTEPINT = 5$.

Cavitation model: pressure recovery model at cavity trailing edge

Variable KCLOFUN is used to select the cavity trailing edge model: $KCLOFUN = 1$ and 2 are available options.

In both cases, ALAMBDA denotes fraction of cavity length in chordwise direction where cavity trailing edge model is applied: $ALAMBDA = 0.3$ yields model applied to 30% of cavity length in the cavity trailing edge region. Suggested values are $0.2 < ALAMBDA < 0.4$.

If $KCLOFUN = 1$, cavity closure model by Kinnas is used: model parameters are specified by variables ACOEF, AGAMMA: typical values are: $ACOE = 0.5$, $AGAMMA = 2.0$.

If $KCLOFUN = 2$, a smooth pressure recovery condition at cavity trailing edge is enforced. In this case, parameters ACOEF and AGAMMA are not used and dummy values can be used.

(see references on cavitation model for details).

Boundary layer modelling

This section will be described in a future version of the manual.

11 Summary of PRO-INS code I/O files (version 1.x)

In the present version of the PRO-INS code manual (version 1.x), some file names are mentioned that could be different from those actually generated by the code.

The following list collects main output files from a non-cavitating flow analysis. String `IT` is used in many file names to identify the time step the file corresponds to. Similarly, string `NC` denotes the iteration step for solution of cavitation algorithm. In case of non-cavitating flow solutions, it is `NC=00`.

- file `bladehubwake.out`: geometry of body and wake
- file `aoa.out`: nominal and effective angle of attack
- file `delphi.t`: circulation along blade span
- file `cpu.IT-NC-00`: pressure on suction side
- file `cp1.IT-NC-00`: pressure on pressure side
- file `press-IT.plt`: pressure on whole body
- file `loads.t`: global rotor loads (propeller case)
- file `pto.out`: global rotor loads (turbine case)

More details from some of these files are given here below. All quantities printed in output files are presented in non-dimensional form following rules described in Section XXX above.

11.1 Description of output file `bladehubwake.out`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: geometry of rotor blade, hub and trailing wake.

Only key-blade and corresponding trailing wake and hub sector (if any) is represented. Cartesian coordinates of grid nodes in the rotating frame of reference.

Suggested visualizer: GNU PLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: x-coordinate
- column no. 2: y-coordinate
- column no. 3: z-coordinate

Blank lines are used to separate different radial sections on blade, different sections on hub and node lines on trailing wake.

11.2 Description of output file `aoa.out`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: distribution along blade span of angles denoting nose-tail pitch of blade sections, nominal inflow, nominal and effective angle of attack. All angles are given in degrees and are measured from a plane normal to rotor axis.

Suggested visualizer: GNUPLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: radius of blade section
- column no. 2: section nose-tail line pitch ϕ_{NT}
- column no. 3: pitch angle of unperturbed inflow ϕ_J
- column no. 4: pitch angle of rotor-perturbed inflow ϕ_i
- column no. 5: nominal angle of attack, defined as $\phi_{NT} - \phi_J$
- column no. 6: effective angle of attack, defined as $\phi_{NT} - \phi_i$

11.3 Description of output file `delphi.t`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: distribution along blade span of circulation.

Suggested visualizer: GNUPLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: time step ΔT
- column no. 2: blade grid index j along span
- column no. 3: radius at grid station j
- column no. 4:
- column no. 5: nominal angle of attack, defined as $\phi_{NT} - \phi_J$
- column no. 6: effective angle of attack, defined as $\phi_{NT} - \phi_i$
- column no. 7...: distribution of circulation on each blade actually solved (can be 1 or Z)

11.4 Description of output file `loads.t`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: rotor thrust, torque coefficients, propeller-like expressions K_T, K_Q, \dots

Suggested visualizer: GNUPLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: advance coefficient (steady-flow analysis), or time step (unsteady-flow analysis)
- column no. 2: propeller thrust coefficient
- column no. 3: propeller torque coefficient (multiplied by factor 10)

- column no. 4: propeller efficiency, $K_T J / 2\pi K_Q$
Other columns after the 4-th are present. Details are not given here.

11.5 Description of output file `pto.out`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: rotor thrust, torque, power coefficients, turbine-like expressions C_T, C_Q, C_P .

Suggested visualizer: GNUPLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: advance coefficient (steady-flow analysis), or time step (unsteady-flow analysis)
- column no. 2: turbine TSR
- column no. 3: turbine thrust coefficient
- column no. 7: turbine torque coefficient
- column no. 11: turbine power coefficient

Other non-dummy columns are present. Details are not given here.

11.6 Description of output files `cpu.IT-NC-00` and `cp1.IT-NC-00`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: distribution of pressure coefficient on blade suction side (file `cpu.IT-NC-00`) and on blade pressure side (file `cp1.IT-NC-00`).

String IT refers to time step, string NC refers to last step of iterative loop of cavitation model algorithm (NC=1 in case of wetted flow analysis).

Suggested visualizer: GNUPLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: chordwise index of blade element (from leading to trailing edge)
- column no. 2: spanwise index of blade element (from root to tip)
- column no. 3: chordwise abscissa (0 at leading edge to 1 at trailing edge)
- column no. 4: spanwise abscissa
- column no. 5: radial position of blade element (fraction of rotor radius)
- column no. 6: value of $-C_p$ at blade element centroid

Note: $-C_p$ is stored instead of C_p .

Blank lines are used to separate different radial sections on blade. In case of steady-flow analysis, one blade is represented; in case of unsteady-flow analysis, all blades are appended to the same file.

11.7 Description of output file `press-IT.plt`

Type: formatted text file.

Description: geometry of rotor and pressure coefficient distribution on rotor blades. Cartesian coordinates of grid nodes in the rotating frame of reference.

String IT refers to time step

Suggested visualizer: TECPLOT

Structure:

- column no. 1: x-coordinate
- column no. 2: y-coordinate
- column no. 3: z-coordinate
- column no. 4: value of $-C_p$ at each node

11.8 Description of output file `hvo1.t` (cavitation)

Type: formatted text file.

Description: cavity extension (area) and volume over rotor blade at each step of iterative loop of cavitation algorithm.

Structure:

- column no. 1: time step
- column no. 2: step of iterative loop of cavitation algorithm
- column no. 3: cavity volume, V_c/D^3
- column no. 4: cavity extension, A_c/D^2

Note: non-dimensional values.

11.9 Description of output file `bubgrd-IT-NC` (cavitation)

Type: formatted text file. TECPLOT format.

Description: geometry of rotor and 3D shape of cavitation bubble limiting surface on rotor blades.

Cartesian coordinates of grid nodes in the rotating frame of reference.

String IT refers to time step, string NC refers to last step of iterative loop of cavitation model algorithm.

Structure:

- column no. 1: x-coordinate
- column no. 2: y-coordinate
- column no. 3: z-coordinate
- column no. 4: value of cavity thickness at each node

Note: non-dimensional values.

For clarity of representation, cavity thickness values is multiplied by a factor 5.

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A AUTOBLADE: screw propeller geometry and grid generation

AUTOBLADE is a software developed at CNR-INSEAN (CNR-INM, from 2018) to generate a 3D model of a rotor, and to build a mesh on its surface.

The rotor is assumed to be composed of an arbitrary number of blades that may be isolated or attached to a finite-length cylindrical hub. Once a 3D model is generated, both blades and hub are discretized into a mesh of quadrilateral elements. The software is valid for both marine propellers and hydrokinetic or wind turbines, and is part of the PRO-INS computational suite developed at CNR-INSEAN for hydrodynamic performance predictions of propellers and turbines.

The present document describes the format of input data that are processed by AUTOBLADE to generate the 3D model and the surface mesh of a given rotor.

Three types of rotors can be processed:

- KPROP = 1: marine propellers from the Wageningen B-series;
- KPROP = 2: marine propellers from the INSEAN series of stock propellers;
- KPROP = 3, 4: generic (*User defined*) propellers and turbines with geometry defined through tables for radial distributions of variables defining the blade planform and tables for blade sectional offsets.

The variable KPROP is used to distinguish among the different cases.

A.1 Wageningen B-Series: KPROP = 1

AUTOBLADE includes a routine specifically dedicated to generate a 3D model according to the geometry definition of Wageningen B-Series screw propellers.

Details of this routine are not given in this version of the document.

A.2 INSEAN Series: KPROP = 2

AUTOBLADE includes a routine specifically dedicated to generate a 3D model according to the geometry definition used at INSEAN for the manufacturing of screw propeller models by using the *Mandelli* CNC machine.

Details of this routine are not given in this version of the document.

A.3 User defined: KPROP = 3

Following a standard approach for marine propellers, the three-dimensional shape of a generic rotor blade can be described by combining two sets of data:

1. radial distributions of geometry parameters defining the blade planform, as pitch, chord, skew, rake, etc. The corresponding input file is indicated here as `filedat.pro`;
2. blade sectional offsets, specified in terms of chordwise distributions of blade thickness and camber at given sections at constant radius. The corresponding input file is indicated here as `filedat.off`.

Different input file names are accepted provided that the extensions `.pro` and `.off` remain.

In addition to blade planform data, the `*.pro` file provides main rotor geometry parameters as number of blades, diameter, hub-to-rotor diameter ratio, rotation orientation. The structure of this input file is as follows:

```

BLADES           ! number of blades
PROPDIAM         ! propeller diameter [m or mm]
RRHUB           ! hub/propeller radius ratio [-]
RIGHTHANDED     ! Is this a righthanded propeller [T/F]
NPS             ! number of radial sections
MPS            ! number of chordwise stations (from LE to TE)
#              ! ... comment string (dummy)
#              ! ... comment string (dummy)
#              ! ... comment string (dummy)
R, PITCH, CHORD, XCLE, TMAX, XCTM, RAKE, FMAX, RLE, RTE ! shape params. at r/R = r_1
R, PITCH, CHORD, XCLE, TMAX, XCTM, RAKE, FMAX, RLE, RTE ! shape params. at r/R = r_2
.....
.....
R, PITCH, CHORD, XCLE, TMAX, XCTM, RAKE, FMAX, RLE, RTE ! shape params. at r/R = r_NPS
    
```

where the geometry parameters are defined as follows ($j \in [1, NPS]$):

- $R = r_j / R_P$
radial position r_j of given section expressed as a fraction of propeller radius R_P ;
- $PITCH = P(r_j) / D_P$
non-dimensional linear pitch P at radius r_j ;
- $CHORD = c(r_j) / D_P$
non-dimensional blade chord at radius r_j ;
- $XCLE = x_{cle}(r_j) / D_P$
non-dimensional location of blade leading edge at radius r_j ;

- $TMAX = t_{max}(r_j)/D_P$
 non-dimensional maximum thickness at radius r_j ;
- $XCTM = x_{ctmax}(r_j)/c(r_j)$
 non-dimensional abscissa of maximum thickness at radius r_j ;
- $RAKE = i(r_j)/D_P$
 non-dimensional linear rake at radius r_j (positive to downstream);
- $FMAX = f_{max}(r_j)/c(r_j)$ is the maximum value of mean line offset at radius r_j .
 This quantity is made non-dimensional with respect to blade chord $c(r_j)$ at same radius.
- $RLE = r_{le}(r_j)/D_P$
 non-dimensional radius of circle tangent to blade profile at leading edge at radius r_j ;
- $RTE = r_{te}(r_j)/D_P$
 non-dimensional radius of circle tangent to blade profile at trailing edge at radius r_j ;

In the present case, geometry type $KPROP = 3$, the following geometry parameters are NOT used:

- TMAX, FMAX, XCTM: the blade section geometry is completely defined through the `filedat.pro` input file (see below).

Dummy values of these variables can be given in the `*.pro` file.

It should be noted that R is the radius fraction, from 0 at rotor axis to 1 at blade tip, whereas shape parameters PITCH, CHORD, XCLE, TMAX, RAKE, RLE, RTE are non-dimensional with respect to propeller diameter D_P .

A graphical definition of geometrical quantities c, x_{cle}, x_{ctmax} is given in Figure 7. It should be noted that blade skew is implicitly defined through quantity x_{cle} .

Blade rake $i(r)$ is defined as the axial displacement of blade section at radius r with respect to blade reference plane. This quantity is assumed to be positive if the blade section is shifted from bow to stern that is, from upstream to downstream.

In addition to blade planform geometry parameters, blade sectional thickness distributions at given radial sections are determined to complete the generation of a 3D model of the rotor blade.

This set of data is given through the input file `*.off`. The file is structured as NPS blocks as follows:

```
#           ! ... comment string (dummy)
#           ! ... comment string (dummy)
X, YB, YF   ! back and face side offsets at x/C = csi_1 [m or mm]
X, YB, YF   ! back and face side offsets at x/C = csi_2 [m or mm]
.....
.....
X, YB, YF   ! back and face side offsets at x/C = csi_MPS [m or mm]
```


Figure 6: Case $KPROP = 3$ and 4: definition of blade sectional profile from suction side, pressure side and mean line offsets given through input files `filedat.off` and `filedat.pro`.

where the following parameters are defined ($i \in [1, MPS]$, $j \in [1, NPS]$):

- $X = x_i/c(r_j)$
chordwise abscissa from leading edge ($X=0$) to trailing edge ($X=1$);
- $YB = yb_i$
offset of blade back (suction) side at abscissa x_i ;
- $YF = yf_i$
offset of blade face (pressure) side at abscissa x_i .

It should be noted that quantities YB , YF are **dimensional** and must be consistent with the value of the rotor diameter given in the `*.pro` file.

Geometry parameters used to define rotor blade sections are illustrated in Fig. 6).

A.4 User defined: $KPROP = 4$

This data format is similar to case $KPROP = 3$ described above. These two formats differ in the definition of the blade section geometry. Specifically, all blade sections are built from a single reference

Figure 7: Definition of blade planform parameters CHORD, XCLE, XCTM, from input file `filedat.pro`.

profile that is defined through chordwise distributions of thickness and camber. These distributions are normalized with a maximum value equal to 1, and the actual values of thickness and camber at each blade radius are obtained through the definition of radial distributions of maximum thickness and camber.

The following quantities are given ($i \in [1, MPS]$ and $j \in [1, NPS]$):

- $X = \xi_i$
 non-dimensional abscissa along blade section, with $X = 0$ denoting leading edge, and $X = 1$ denoting trailing edge;
- $YB = y_b(\xi_i)$
 Normalised value of back (suction) side offset at non-dimensional abscissa ξ_i ;
 The dimensional value of offset is evaluated by: $YB \times \frac{1}{2} TMAX \times PROPDIAM$;
- $YF = y_f(\xi_i)$

Normalised value of face (pressure) side offset at non-dimensional abscissa ξ_i ;

The dimensional value of offset is evaluated by: $YF \times \frac{1}{2} TMAX \times PROPDIAM$;

- $FC = f_c(\xi_i)$

Normalised value of mean line offset at non-dimensional abscissa ξ_i ;

The dimensional value of offset is evaluated by: $FC \times FMAX \times CHORD$, where CHORD is the value of blade chord at local radius (i.e., $c(r_j)$).

Note that both YB, YF, FC values in file `filedat.off` are normalized, i.e., with values between 0 and 1 (YB, FC) or -1 (YF) according to standard sign conventions (see Fig. 6): pressure side (face) offsets, YF, are negative, and suction side (back) offsets, YB, are positive; mean-line offsets can be positive or negative (as an example, a positive mean-line offset is sketched in Fig. 6).

The structure of input file `*.off` is:

```
NBASEOFF      ! number of reference profiles (fixed to 1)
MPS           ! number of chordwise stations (from LE to TE)
#            ! ... comment string (dummy)
#            ! ... comment string (dummy)
#            ! ... comment string (dummy)
X, YB, YF, FC ! ascissa, back, face, mean-line offsets at station x_1
X, YB, YF, FC ! ascissa, back, face, mean-line offsets at station x_2
.....
.....
X, YB, YF, FC ! ascissa, back, face, mean-line offsets at station x_MPS
```

It should be noted that quantity MPS from file `*.off` must be identical to same quantity indicated in file `*.pro`.

Once reference suction side, pressure side and mean line offsets are defined, a profile is built as shown in Fig. 6.

A.5 Definition of propeller hub

Once a three-dimensional representation of blades is obtained, propeller hub and hub/blade connection details are specified.

Here, the simple case of a conical hub is considered. Geometrical quantities necessary to manufacture the propeller hub are sketched in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Sketch of propeller hub geometrical characteristics.